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(Poor) accounting for God: the tracking and monitoring of cash flows in the Custody of the Holy Land's network (1650s–1680s)

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the issues of accountability and solvency in the early modern period by focusing on a religious entity, the Franciscan Custody of the Holy Land, and on its peripheral branches, the *commissariati*. The Custody was a sort of long-distance international proto-corporation that had to periodically prove its good administration to the Roman *Curia* while keeping a certain margin of autonomy and independence. The analysis of the *commissariati*'s accounting records, which registered all transactions and were periodically sent to Rome for scrutiny, shows how these documents were crafted to serve the friars' own narrative of their tenure, to promote their endeavours, and to reach a precarious balance between economic solvency, administrative flexibility, and decisional autonomy. The drafting of their balances, for instance, was partially altered to show always minimally positive values. The flexibility of the charge-and-discharge system helped to reach this goal. The research is based on the records of the *commissariati* of Naples, Messina, and Genoa that were sent for auditing between 1654 and 1687. The Custody's sources of revenues, along with the credit instruments in play, shed further light on the multiple entanglements between religious and secular authorities on local and global scales in this period.

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Introduction

Repayment of debts is commonly perceived as an obligation grounded in moral or religious principles (Robe and Steiger 2015). Ancient Hindu jurisprudence, for example, allowed for the execution of a debtor and the subsequent enslavement of his spouse. In Judaism, although there is a provision for the periodic cancellation of debts owed by the impoverished, the ethical duty to settle one's debts persists. In Islam, God is a witness to any contract entered into by individuals; therefore, failing to respect an agreement is a sinful action (Koran II: 282). Christians are bound by the same obligation (Romans 13:7). The Lord's

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prayer refers to solvency – in its generic meaning – as a quality of the faithful: ‘forgive us our trespasses [‘debts’, in Latin] as we forgive those who trespass against us’.

All these individual behaviours fall under the concept of economic solvency, which is a relevant concern for most religious beliefs. Such beliefs influence all judgements people make in their lives (Connolly 1999), including corporate decision making (Conroy and Emerson 2004; Longenecker, McKinney, and Moore 2004; Elnahas, Hassan, and Ismail 2017). For instance, McGuire, Omer, and Sharp (2012) found a negative association between religiosity and financial reporting irregularities.

The concept of solvency is relatively recent in its definition and is of great importance for corporate entities, although it is predominantly associated with the insurance field (Sandström 2006), rather than with religious organisations. Its first appearance in English dates back to Bailey et al. (1721), who defined it as ‘being able to make payments’. Benjamin (1977) refers to the *Oxford English Dictionary*, where solvency is equated with ‘having money enough to meet all pecuniary liabilities’. Its definition is also discussed in the report for the OEEC written by Campagne (1961, chap. 1). Solvency is a critical indicator of financial health, as it demonstrates an entity’s capability to sustain its operations well into the long term. Gryglewicz (2011) defines corporate solvency as the ability to cover debt obligations in the long run. Pentikäinen (1967) states that this concept can be framed from the management of the company’s perspective, for whom the aim would be the continuation of the function and existence of the company, or from the supervising authorities’ perspective: in this latter case, the benefits of the claimants and policyholders have priority over the firm’s survival. In the first case, the objective is pursued on the long term. The second perspective requires the firm to meet its obligations for a short period (Pentikäinen 1984).

Solvency does not equate to liquidity, that is the availability of cash. If, at any time, a firm is unable to pay its obligations, it is illiquid (Gryglewicz 2011). If it is not able to cover debt obligations in the long run, it becomes insolvent and it defaults:

Short-term liquidity shocks affect the expected cash flow rate through Bayesian learning. More specifically, it is assumed that cash flows follow a Brownian motion with drift and that the drift parameter is not directly observable. The firm and investors observe noisy cash flows (subject to liquidity shocks) and learn about the drift (the average rate of cash flows). In this way, short-term liquidity shocks around average profitability are not only noise but also, if persistent, affect the assessment of solvency. (Gryglewicz 2011, 366)

This study deals with the concepts of economic solvency from an organisational and accounting perspective. It addresses the following research question: how did a religious institution with a functioning similar to that of a long-distance corporation operate with regard to solvency and accounting supervision by an external authority? A possible answer is by building a façade of solvency, ‘fabricated’ to comply with corporate strategies in front of the supervising institution. I will show how this goal could be reached by taking into account a case study, the branches of the *Custodia Terrae Sanctae* (Custody of the Holy Land), and their relationships with a supervising authority, the *Congregatio de Propaganda Fide* (PF). The way these branches compiled and sent their accounting records to PF helped them building a narrative centred on solvency and good administration.

Coping with liquidity shocks and debts, as the Custody frequently did, is even more important when scrutinising the economic activities of religious organisations, where

money and profit have to be justified and employed for the common good of the Christian community (*charitas*) (Todeschini 2002). The Jesuit Order, for instance, founded in 1540, is usually referred to as ‘the first Christian global Order’ using a modern accounting technique – double-entry bookkeeping – and giving importance to concepts such as good accounting to keep the distance from ‘sinful’ wealth (Quattrone 2004, 675). Other religious orders, including the Franciscans, used older accounting techniques, such as the charge-and-discharge system, to provide a record of their good faith while promoting the growth of their enterprise.¹ The fact that the charge-and-discharge accounting system has been defined as less demanding and sophisticated (Quattrone 2004, 672) does not necessarily mean that it entailed archaic or unsophisticated management (Lenoble 2013, 120). As early as the thirteenth century, the leaders of the Franciscan Order emphasised the importance of good administration, requiring their ministers to regularly present their account books (Lenoble 2013, 93). Accountability was a precious concept in religious organisations, as should be solvency, despite the different techniques adopted and the fact that St. Francis’ ideas in late medieval Europe have been contextualised as a direct reaction against the monetarisation and marketisation of his socio-economic environment (Todeschini 2004).

In the last decade, journals, ledgers, and income-expense notebooks written by religious organisations have mostly attracted those interested in ecclesiastical, art, architecture, and cultural history (Melchiorre 2016). It was only recently that an increasing number of studies focused on accounting and accountability practices in religious entities.² However, the figure remains comparatively modest relative to the widespread presence of religious institutions in pre-industrial societies (Parker 2002; Carmona and Ezzamel 2006). Moreover, most of these studies focus either on the micro – on how accounting has influenced religious organisations’ functioning – or on the macro scale – on how religious thought has influenced business and social contexts – without taking into account the dynamic interplay related to the strategies adopted by these organisations, or other concepts such as economic solvency (Bertrand 2004, 149; Cordery 2015, 431).

Research on accounting and economic management in religious institutions often classifies the latter under the umbrella of nonprofit organisations (Quattrone 2004, 648).³ The Custody does not fit into this model as it pursued solvency while handling significant – albeit irregular – cash flows to make the profits necessary for new investments and the buying of lands and houses, all to strengthen the friars’ presence in the Holy Land.

The Custody is a Franciscan Province, that is a supranational Catholic territorial organisational unit, founded in 1217 by St. Francis. Over the following decades, the friars settled mainly in Jerusalem and Bethlehem. Their institution aimed at being Jerusalem’s gatekeeper for Christians (Armstrong 2021, 5) and a kind of commercial hub. Today, the Custody comprises territories belonging to Cyprus, Egypt, Israel, Jordan, Lebanon, Palestine, Syria, Turkey, and Rhodes.

Since 1517, the Custody was administered by the Observant branch of the Franciscan order, which was characterised by the aspiration to live a secluded life with strict control over the use of property.⁴ It kept good relations with Ottoman and religious local authorities, checked the number and behaviour of pilgrims, and provided material and financial support to those arriving from Christendom (Evangelisti 2020b, 36). During this period, several factors pushed the friars of the Custody towards a stringent adherence to financial accountability and fiscal stability (Tejirian and Simon 2012), such as changes in

the early modern European economy, coupled with the growing assimilation of the Mediterranean into global trade networks; the arrival of missionaries in the Middle East; and the Custody's engagement in missionary activities.⁵

During the seventeenth century, the Custody had to constantly prove to be a financially stable institution in front of other Catholic institutions and the Franciscan Order, who theoretically prohibited its fundraising branches, called *commissariati*, to recur to indebtedness. Their money had to be used for the payment of the Custody's debts (Vagnari vol. III/1, 445).⁶ In addition to the Order, PF was the other Catholic institution involved in the supervising of the Custody's activities. Initially led by 13 cardinals, PF was created in 1622 in Rome by Pope Gregory XV to control missionary activities on a global scale (Metzler 1971). According to Pizzorusso (2022, 101), it performed governance functions, such as the supervision of economic endeavours of religious orders. For the Custody, showing solvency in front of a supervising authority – even at the risk of manipulating the timing of the accounts' delivery – and effective cash flow management was crucial. The mismanagement of the resources sent to the Holy Land was one of the accusations levelled by the Reformed branch of the Order and other Catholic institutions against the Observant to challenge their control over the Custody (Armstrong 2021, 307–321). These elements make the Custody an interesting example of an early modern institution that operated on long distances far from the frontier of the European world and managed to preserve its economic solvency, administrative flexibility, and decisional autonomy over time.

To handle its wide array of activities, the Custody needed consistent cash flows and a sound organisational structure based on aforementioned multiple fundraising branches, called *commissariati*. Throughout the study, I analyse the available accounting records produced by the European *commissariati* and sent to PF between 1654 and 1687 to answer the research question and shed light on the accounting techniques, the organisational strategies, and the economic functioning of part of the Custody's network. The analysis, based on understudied sources, also allows me to look at how much the *commissariati* relied on the local economies and institutions that provided them with consistent but irregular cash flows.

The Custody's long-term solvency, reached primarily thanks to its Catholic secular sponsors, relied on the correct management of cash flows from the *commissariati*. The latter, located in the various Franciscan provinces across the globe, were (and still are) responsible for collecting assets, organising their transport to the convent of St. Saviour in Jerusalem, and facilitating and controlling the circulation of friars going to the Middle East and back. They have been defined as the 'immobile infrastructure' of the Custody's network, operating via maritime routes (Tramontana 2023a). The Franciscans' own rhetoric and pursuit of an idealised poverty should not obscure their entanglements within the European imperial projects as they developed across the Mediterranean, the Atlantic, and Asia (McClure 2019). The Custody's location, along with those of the European *commissariati* in the seventeenth century and the places cited in this study, are shown on Figure 1. More *commissariati*, on which we have only scattered information, operated in Goa (Quecedo 1951), as well as in Central and Southern America (Villela 2015; Melvin 2022).

Despite their quantity, this study focuses on the *commissariati* of Genoa, Messina, and Naples. The selection of these port cities is based on their pivotal role in the Custody's

Figure 1. The Custody's network, seventeenth century.

Source: Elaboration of the author.

network during the second half of the seventeenth century and on the abundance of available sources. Most assets sent to the Holy Land converged from Spain, Rome, and outside Europe to the Tyrrhenian *commissariati* in countries under Spanish influence – such as the viceroyalties of Naples and Sicily, or the Republic of Genoa (Dauverd 2015). This period also marked a strong commitment by PF to keep track of the Custody's finances.⁷ The sources facilitate both a synchronous analysis for specific years in the 1650s and, in the case of Genoa, a diachronic analysis spanning a longer period (1650s–1680s). Although there is an abundance of studies on the Custody – not so many on its economic endeavours – almost no research has been done on the *commissariati*, despite the significant number of assets and cash flows which they handled.⁸ The studies that have looked at – among other things – their activities have focused on the macro aspects of the *commissariati's* functioning, for example from a legal, political and diplomatic point of view, often emphasising the influence of Spain and France, the defence of the Custody's privileges or the conflicts between religious orders (García Barriuso 1992; Armstrong 2021; Melvin 2022). Micro economic data were taken into account occasionally and by way of example. An exception in this sense, and this is the direction in which my contribution is headed, are the works of Tramontana (2023a; 2023b), who uses economic data issued from the *commissariati's* accounts as the starting point to construct broader and original interpretative frameworks on mobility networks.

The use of accounting sources allows me to move beyond the rhetorical arguments expressed by narrative sources such as books, administrative correspondence, reports and memoirs sent to Rome, to elucidate how the *commissariati* were profoundly influenced and shaped by the economic, social, and political fabric within which they operated. This study is developed through five sections. The one that follows this paragraph provides an overview of the Custody's functioning, which evokes the features of early modern long-distance corporations.⁹ The subsequent section is devoted to a critical

analysis of the sources, and one to the methodology used, followed by the analysis of the data. Such analysis also takes into account typical interactions between local or supranational institutions and the *commissariati* to illustrate how their operations were shaped by the local economies in a symbiotic relationship. The last section presents the main findings of the analysis by linking them to the research question and the objectives of the study: arguing how the *commissariati*'s accounting records were produced and delivered to showcase their positive balances and avoid a tutorship from Rome. The conclusions reflect on the complexities of the economic context within which the *commissariati* were situated and how their accounting techniques mirror specific behaviours and management strategies.

The Custody of the Holy Land as an early modern proto-corporation?

In 1620, according to Roger (1646, 378–380), there were between 90 and 110 Franciscans in the Holy Land, headed by a Custodian (*Custos*) elected every three years. Similar figures are attested in 1680, with 125 friars and *terziari*, who were lay members of the order occupied with craftwork and economic activities. The Custody pursued a long-term capitalisation strategy, with frequent purchases of land and buildings through indebtedness on the local financial market, in which the friars acted as lenders and borrowers (Evangelisti 2020b). As the Jesuits did in Asia, they were local economic actors (Tramontana 2020; Evangelisti 2020b).

The Custody's network was not limited to the Eastern Mediterranean regions. Instead, it relied heavily on its branches in Western Europe. Thus, its functioning can be better understood by framing the theoretical similitude with early modern long-distance corporations. A long-standing debate surrounds the origin of such corporations and links it to several influences, among which the Catholic Church plays a relevant role.¹⁰ Some historians view the Roman Catholic Church as a large business enterprise, while others consider the Jesuits as a typical Catholic religious corporation (Ekelund et al. 1996; Quattrone 2004). The corporation structure provided religious organisations with autonomy from the Papacy and, at the same time, from territorial rulers (Pettigrew and Veevers 2019, 20–21; Taviani 2022, 1).¹¹ Based on their governance rules, the collective bodies of the Roman Church became entitled to own property, to convey it to third parties, and to litigate disputes with such third parties. These collective entities were not restricted by geographical boundaries or individual lifespans, offering significant benefits for an institution where celibacy was mandatory and the inheritance of titles and property was prohibited (Harris 2020, 257).

The Custody's statute of 1526, called *pro Terra Sancta*, confirmed the custodian's authority as a Provincial Minister answering directly to the heads of the Order (Golubovich 1898, XXIII). In addition to the custodian in Jerusalem, the statute mentioned for the first time a Venetian *commissariato* (García Barriuso 1992, 46) and a procurator in Sicily, tasked specifically with securing alms from the Holy Roman Emperor (Quaresmi 1639, 475). The General Chapter of 1645 issued a decree that completed the Custody's organisational chart (Figure 2), at least for the second half of the seventeenth century (Vaginari 1650, 49–50). The three top charges were those of the custodian, the vicar, and the procurator general. The custodian had to be Italian. He was appointed by the Order's *Definitorio* and confirmed by PF. He remained in office for three years and had the double title of

Figure 2. Organisational chart of the Custody of the Holy Land, seventeenth century.

Source: Elaboration of the author.

regular superior and prefect of the missions of the Near East. When he was not in Jerusalem, his place was taken by a custodial president elected by the *discretorio*, the governing body where all relevant issues were discussed. The vicar, who had to be of French origin, assisted the custodian. The third office of the Custody was that of the procurator general, of Spanish origin, whose task was to administer the finances. In addition to the three major charges already mentioned, the vicar and the procurator general appointed two more friars for the *discretorio*, one Spanish and one French. This division by countries of origin guaranteed representation to those who contributed most to the Custody's existence, while sanctioning the diminishing importance of Venice and the networks dependent on the Holy Roman Empire.¹² The *discretorio* remained in office for three years, renewable once, and met ordinarily on a weekly basis.¹³

During the seventeenth century, *commissariati* were created in Naples, Genoa, Florence, Malta, and so on, as can be seen in Figure 1, following the increasing integration of the Mediterranean into global trading networks and the emergence of international rivalries in the sponsorship of Franciscan missions between Catholic states. On a greater scale compared to the previous century, the network reflects two main concerns, beyond the obvious Catholic affiliation of the *commissariati*'s regions: proximity to the Mediterranean networks, and the inclusion of cities where the main Catholic rulers resided, such as Paris, Vienna, and Madrid.

The Custody and its *commissariati* were accountable to several European institutions: the Franciscan Order, PF, and the European rulers that sponsored the friars' endeavours in Palestine. Among the latter, the Spanish Kings played a key role. The Custodian, in 1629, wrote that the latter was 'the legitimate King of Jerusalem, Patron [...] of those Sacred Places and of the Observant clergymen [...] who inhabit them' (García Barriuso 1992, 5). In exchange for Spanish support, the *commissariato* in Madrid was almost autonomous

from Rome in sending alms and had deep connections with the *commissariati* in the Spanish viceroyalties of Naples and Messina. The *commissario* of Messina, because of its tight connection with Spain, paid double monitoring costs by sending extracts of the accounts to Madrid, in addition to Rome.¹⁴ When, between 1619 and 1622, PF decided to centralise the collection of alms in Rome by bypassing the *commissariato* in Madrid, the King of Spain stopped sending money altogether. The Custodian reported:

I have written to almost all the Princes and to those who are obliged to help and remedy this damage so evident and so detrimental to Christianity and its reputation [...], but now it seems that none of them has heard me. (García Barriuso 1992, 228)

The Custodian's autonomy, therefore, was limited.

Each *commissariato* relied on local procurators to collect alms, and had deep connections with secular and religious institutions that provided significant revenues or services.

The structure of the Custody was further developed in 1621 with the *Statuta generalia pro locis Terrae Sanctae*, also known as Constitutions of Segovia, enacted under the leadership of the General Minister of the Franciscan Order, Benigno of Genoa (Vaginari 1650, 664–666). Before becoming a friar, Benigno served as an accountant for a Genoese merchant in Sicily. His professional background likely played a role in shaping the drafting of the new statutes, which, for the first time, regulated various economic and accounting facets of collecting and recording alms (Cagnetti 1966).

The *commissari* – elected by the Order with the approval of PF – were required to be pious and humble, as well as skilled in accounting, possibly with experience in commercial exchanges. Each of them was sided by a *sindaco* and a 'companion'. The *sindaco* was usually a layman, sometimes a priest or a *terziario* (Carni 2008). As was the case with Claude-Denis Cochin (Moracchini 2021) and the family dynasties found in the sources examined, the *commissariat's* *sindaci* had a distinct sociological profile, usually being merchants or businessmen respected by the community.¹⁵ Every *sindaco* designated a deputy commissary in his province, who was tasked with overseeing the search, provision, and collection of alms by local procurators. The *commissari* and the *sindaci* were required to count the alms in the presence of the chief or provincial minister of their nation every semester, before sending them to the *sindaco* in Venice or Messina (Vaginari 1650, 665).

Deputy *commissari* were required to present their books for scrutiny at the provincial chapter of the Franciscan Order. The latter verified and sent them sealed to the general commissaries (Cecchinato forthcoming). The *commissari*, in turn, brought them to the General Chapter, that is the periodically convened elective and legislative assembly of all friars. At this stage, the Order's *Definitorio Generale*, that is the collegial governing body made up of elected members from the General Chapter, conducted – in theory – a thorough examination of the account books.¹⁶ Additionally, starting from 1654, a decree by PF required each *commissario* the periodical sending to Rome of accounts for scrutiny.¹⁷ The graphical representation of the Custody's structure is shown in Figure 2.

The complex structure aiming at governing a composite group over very long distances – a total of 18 people between general *commissari* and general *sindaci*, 100 deputy *commissari*, and an indefinite number of local *sindaci* – evokes those of other European early modern long-distance corporations. The Custody, albeit under the authority of the Order, even enjoyed a global monopoly on the production and selling of objects and

books related to the Holy Land (Heyberger 2021; Melvin 2022). Its governing body served a public interest by assisting Christian pilgrims in the Holy Land and operated independently of the Order to which it belonged, although the Order appointed the Custodian and checked the accounts. Depending on the degree of autonomy enjoyed by the Custodian, which could also vary based on who was appointed to this charge, the Custody could be considered as a corporation per se or as a division of a bigger corporation, that was the Franciscan Order. Despite this issue, on which more research is needed, the Custody's functioning complies with the distinctive qualities constituting the corporate sociology for global interaction of trading corporations (Pettigrew and Veevers 2019, 19): being subordinated to state authority at home and abroad; engaging in negotiations with external constituencies; having constitutions to facilitate the effective structuring; being autonomous from oversight of the domicile state; and having an integrative functioning that connects global and local realities. In particular, the following characteristics apply to the Custody: its subordination to European, Ottoman, and Papal powers made it compliant, or rather obedient, to state authority both domestically and internationally. Secondly, the Custody engaged in ceaseless negotiations with external parties, such as merchants, shipmasters, consuls, dragomans, and other religious orders. Thirdly, the friars possessed statutes that enabled the structured management of their international engagements. Fourthly, the Custody functioned independently in the Holy Land, operating within the jurisdictional interstices among states and crafting its own corporate identity, although it was periodically subject to approval and review by the Order or other powers. Lastly, the Custody functioned integratively, bridging global dynamics with local, regional, and national interests, as can be seen in relation to the *commissariati's* financing.

Accountability played a crucial role in sustaining this multifaceted organisation, particularly given its long-distance and multi-branch structure (Roberts 1991). Essential to its governance was the written and/or verbal exchange of explanations about a past event to prevent or avoid conflict stemming from differences between the principal's expectations and the performance or behaviour of the agent (Messner 2009). Berkhofer III (2004) argues that the idea and practice of accountability contributed to the transformation from bad to good lordship, since it reduced dishonest behaviours. Accounting also facilitated the separation of religious orders from their wealth by providing visibility to the flows of goods, services, and money (Quattrone 2004, 673). The friars could uphold their vow of poverty while engaging in profit-making endeavours. However, their accounting technique and the discrepancies among the accounting records they sent to PF also reflect how they shaped their power relation with Rome.¹⁸ That is why, to fully comprehend the Custody's governance and its engagement in global interactions, it is essential to examine the sources underpinning these activities, particularly accounting records, as they offer critical insights into the mechanisms of accountability, power dynamics, and resource management within this organisational framework.

Sources

PF sought to implement the Papal project of a centralised administration of missionary activities – with a direct economic management supervision – to promote the effectiveness of the pope's universal authority (Pizzorusso 2022, 100). Financial administration was one of the main issues over which the religious legitimacy of the Observants' government

of the Custody was challenged and scrutinised. Other religious orders and reformed Franciscan friars frequently accused the Custody of mismanagement, with the latter having to demonstrate its honest behaviour by producing accounting records in an ostensibly impeccable manner (Heyberger 1994; Armstrong 2021).

These elements partially emerge through the analysis of the accounting extracts sent between the 1650s and 1680s from the *commissariati* of Genoa (La Pace), Naples (Monte Calvario), and Messina (Santa Maria di Gesù).¹⁹ Extracts were drafted according to a simplified charge-and-discharge structure. The latter is a method of bookkeeping, also known as the stewardship method, widely used in the late medieval period by landlords, whose main goal was to control the behaviour of agents and detect possible fraud. The point of charge-and-discharge is to categorise flows of money and/or other assets into ordered groups through three distinct stages. First, the agent (administrator) was charged with what he had received or been paid; later on, he was discharged with what he had spent and paid. Finally, the difference, referred to as the balance, was computed. The balance denoted the value of what the agent owed his master or vice versa (Baker and Eadsforth 2011). The settlement of that difference resolved the accumulated obligation, reinstated the symmetry of positions in both stages, and concluded the agent's responsibility (Llibrer Escrig and Villaluenga de Gracia 2023, 7). I refer to a simplified structure given that the *commissariati's* accounting records have very few categories, being almost a simple list of revenues and expenditures in chronological order. In the Genoese *commissariato*, for instance, the *sindaco* separated charges on alms from parishes from those from Genoese institutions.²⁰

From a religious and moral point of view, charge-and-discharge is a relationship in which there is a delegation by the owner (God-lord) to the agent (servant) (Villaluenga de Gracia 2013), according to the same system used by the Christians to give account to God during confession. As such, it did not support a mercantile mentality (Aho 2005; Miley and Read 2016). Nevertheless, it offered several other advantages: it was a simple technique that could follow chronological order, disclosed relevant information, neutralised imbalances arising from agency relationships, prevented overspending and embezzlement, revealed cash flows, and – in theory – facilitated decision making (Llibrer Escrig and Villaluenga de Gracia 2019). In large entities, the charge-and-discharge technique simplified decentralised management by functional areas or independent cash management offices (Llibrer Escrig and Villaluenga de Gracia 2023, 13), as the *commissariati*. The latter's accounts partially escaped such features because, as mentioned, very few categories were used.

Each accounting extract began with a statement from the *sindaci*. According to PF instructions, they should clearly show the 'total, quality and quantity of alms [...] so that the balance and judgement on the administration of one's office is valid and can be reported to anyone in a correct form'.²¹ The *sindaci* did not use the term charge or discharge, but refer directly to their own cash management and used the expressions 'debts' (*debito*) and 'income' (*introito*), to refer to the money that they anticipated for the expenses of the *commissariato* or received as alms. They remitted surpluses – or reporting outstanding debts – from the previous management at the opening and closing of their account extracts.²² According to Jones (1985), the use of charge and discharge is simply an accounting convention whose etymology is not clear and which is used in different senses by different writers. The first entry was usually the balance brought forward

from the foot of the previous period's account. The distinction between sections is clear, and subtotals are marked at the end of each page and recalled on top of the following one. The charge section reports the parishes, institutions and individuals who sent money to the *commissariato*. The discharge section contain entries linked to the persons or institutions to which the money was given, or for which it was spent. Each entry is in paragraph form and associated with a cash basis, even when the donation is in kind, as in the case of silk or wheat. All figures are in Roman numerals in columns separated between main and sub-units. Genoese *lire*, *soldi* and *denari*, for instance, are strictly segregated. The final elements were the balance – called also *saldo* or *consolidatio* in the sources – and the declaration of truthfulness with the signature of the *sindaco* and the *commissario*. The records are suitable for assessing solvency in each *commissariato*, rather than in the Custody as a whole, because each branch acted as an independent office and kept track of existing creditors. Evidence also exists of money transfers between *commissariati* to face exceptional expenses in order to avoid insolvency.²³

Regularity and standardisation in the accounts were necessary to keep the Custody's network under supervision. However, it was common for the *sindaci* to write that they were 'not skilled in abacus', that the account books were kept in bad material conditions (*assai stracciati*), or to send them for scrutiny with irregular timings.²⁴ The latter is the aspect on which I will focus to highlight the *commissariati's* strategy. I believe that, as all the *commissariati* relied on irregular cash flows, the *sindaci* sometimes chose to send their records at the most convenient intervals to show the *commissariati's* constant capacity to face their liabilities in time. PF required them to send an extract of their accounting records every two years in January, after Christmas holidays.²⁵ The accounts sent in June 1666 by Nicolò and Giovanni Francesco Croce, *sindaci* in the *commissariato* of Genoa, were refused because of their wrong timing:

In July of the same year, I sent these accounts to Father Giustitia, then commissioner of the Holy Land in Rome; and he did not present them [to PF], because he told me that the accounts were due in January and that I should send him the accounts for the missing months in due course [...].²⁶

PF repeatedly attempted to standardise information gathering, as it did with missions in general (Pizzorusso 2022), but many *commissariati* kept following irregular behaviours.²⁷ Some of them, like the *commissariato* of France, explicitly refused to send the accounts to PF because they did not recognise its authority at all.²⁸

In everyday practice, accounting records had even more peculiarities that make comparison difficult, also because of the charge-and-discharge structure. Records do not allow for evaluation and analysis of profits and losses to improve the economic performance (Lemarchand 1994; Gervais 2021). Therefore, it presented technical deficiencies to attend to all the information requirements requested by PF (Hernández-Esteve 2000), which in the long run aimed at direct economic management (Pizzorusso 2022, 100) and at the use of accounting for management purposes (Gervais 2020, 264). Most entries in *sindaci's* records prevented the establishment of relationships between debtor and creditor parties, or the perception of the unit or whole; also, the unique position of the person who returned debt and credit amounts at the same time cannot be visualised (Hernández-Esteve 2013).

An example is the manufacture of two baldachins for Jerusalem, one red and one white, made in Genoa between 1685 and 1687. These precious liturgical objects, commissioned by the custodian himself, were made over three years. Information on the costs for raw materials and on the wages for the embroiderers, gilders, and craftsmen involved are spread over 25 entries in two records sent to PF in different periods. The expenses are very detailed, such as the payment of six Genoese *lire* to the consuls of the embroiderers' guild for an estimate, or that of the paper for wrapping the baldachins before shipping. However, fully realising how these expenses were managed over such a long period of time and retrieving the data scattered among hundreds of entries make information gathering – on the total manufacturing costs, on the relationship with the artisans involved, on the temporary contraction of debts, and so on – very difficult. Some entries even refer to only one of the two baldachins, without specifying which one. PF auditors in Rome could only monitor how the work was progressing and that the overall balance did not go into deficit because of this expenditure, which in total amounted to 1,951 Genoese *lire* (about 390 pieces of eight). PF accountants often complained about the difficulty in checking the records and the fact that if there were mistakes they did not know who to ask for explanations (Carnevali forthcoming).

Methodology

As mentioned in the introduction, this study considers the concept of solvency as the basis of the relationship between the *commissariati* of the Holy Land and PF. I believe that, in addition to be accountable for the proper destination of alms in connection with the payments made with them, the *commissariati* also wanted to show their ability to face their expenses over time, that is to remain solvent. Through the analysis of the account extracts they produced, I show how the *commissariati* chose the best timings to reassure the Roman authorities on the good handling of their accounts and

Figure 3. Comparison between the *commissariato* of Genoa's balances sent to PF and calculations based on available data, 1654–1687.

Source: Elaboration of the author based on data in Appendices 1 and 2.

how they were able to face their expenses when they come due. PF and the other Catholic religious orders criticised the Custody's functioning, so the records that the *commissariati* sent to Rome had to reflect stable cash flows (Figure 3).

The *commissariati's* extracts are still preserved in PF archives today, although unfortunately there are many gaps. For this reason, I chose to focus on the records sent by those of Genoa, Naples and Messina. For Genoa, there is an almost uninterrupted series from 1654 to 1687. For Messina and Naples, many extracts are missing. I have used those available from 1651 to 1661 for Naples, and from 1657 to 1660 for Messina. The original account books from which the extracts were drawn are not available, and, at the moment, further research in the archives of Genoa, Naples, and Messina has proved unsuccessful.

All data from each record were digitised in Excel files and categorised according to their nature (gross funds, payments, donations, alms, etc.). This operation has been conducted by the ERC HolyLab research team, which will publish all the records in an open access database.²⁹ My first operation was to reconstruct the trend of the amounts recorded in the records by taking into account entries approximating income and expenses (Appendix 1). For example, I checked but I did not take into account the balances brought forward from the foot of the previous period's accounts, which were always small, in order to avoid repetitions and to have a picture of only the cash flows in a given period. In the records examined, there is no mention of information such as who covered the negative difference between charge and discharge, or of respites (Noke 1991; 1996).

Each *commissariato* drafted the accounting records in its own currency. To compare them, it was necessary to convert all currencies – Genoese *lire*, Sicilian *onze*, Neapolitan *ducats* – into Spanish silver pieces of eight. I chose this currency given that it is the only one that is mentioned – with its equivalence – in at least one record per location. Where the conversion rate for a year was not available, I calculated it by averaging the conversion rates between the previous and the following year. In the case of Genoa, it was also possible to rely on the conversion tables of Giacchero (1979).

The *commissariati* drafted their balances according to irregular timings. To compare cash flow trends over time and between different places, I reordered the records based on the date of each entry and selected semester periods. I chose semester rather than annual periods to cope with the scattering of data. Often some months per year are missing, and this absence would have resulted in interpolations or the discarding of a significant amount of data. Such an operation was also possible because the *commissariati's* accounts are based on cash flows rather than on farming or other products, so they did not depend on seasonality. Even the *sindaci*, as mentioned, were theoretically required to count the alms every semester.

Finally, a qualitative analysis of the entries that constituted the main charges follows. This operation is aimed at explaining the irregularity in the cash flows and at showing the level of dependence of the *commissariati* on the public institutions of the states in which they were located. I chose to compare the median values of the records because the average was too much influenced by the irregularity of the data. This analysis was not carried out for the discharge sections, since the latter reflect the functioning of the Custody, which, in most cases, could choose the times in which to face its expenses and did not depend so strongly on local institutions.

Data analysis

The timings of the balances issued from the records available for Genoa, Naples, and Messina, are all different and irregular. The irregularity prevents any comparison regarding cash flows and balances over time, so much that PF complained about the ‘very substantial doubts’ arising during their revision.³⁰

In Naples, only 2 records out of 10 (excluding those for which we do not have the corresponding dates of charge and discharge) are drawn up at vaguely biannual intervals. The same applies to the accounts of Genoa. Sicily has perhaps the most detailed records, probably due to the higher circulation of money. Most alms – especially currencies – from Spain and Italy converged on Messina before being shipped to the Holy Land. Out of 12 records of Naples, 17 of Messina and 28 of Genoa, there is only one negative balance, for an extremely low amount: 1.5 pieces of eight in Genoa in 1669. Every time significant revenues appeared, equally significant outgoings followed, and vice versa.

The reordering and analysis of records on a semestral basis revealed a much more complex and varied situation than the one emerging from the tamed extracts sent irregularly to Rome. Based on the semesters for which all the necessary information are available, a significant – and very similar – proportion of balance deficits emerges. In Genoa, 18 out of 42 balances (39 per cent) were in deficit; in Naples, 6 out of 14 (42 per cent); in Messina, 3 out of 7 (42 per cent). In those cases, an outstanding debt with the *sindaco* would have been recorded who, as already mentioned, anticipated the expenses on behalf of the *commissario*. The gaps in the data are minimal and wide fluctuations occur, as can be seen in [Figure 3](#) for what concern Genoese balances, that is the *commissariato* for which more data have been preserved.

In everyday practice, regular revenues were frequently insufficient and each *commissariato* survived thanks to payment made in advance by the *sindaci* out of their own money and sporadic donations by local institutions. Surpluses guaranteed by institutional donations exceeded expenditures and allowed to repay outstanding debts, so there was no need to mask the occasional deficits. Still, each *commissariato* sent balances at irregular timing to show a regularly positive trend, so that no one could question the way money was spent. Let us illustrate with an example. The Genoese account extract of 1686 recorded the equivalent of 123.6 pieces of eight from the balance brought forward from the previous period. At the end of the year, however, the discharges were of around 30 pieces of eight higher than the sum of the charges recorded in the same period and of the previous balance. Still, the document closed in 1688 with a positive balance.

The irregularities of the cash flows further emerge through the qualitative analysis of the main entries in the charge sections. The first thing to note is the different size of the flows. The figures in the following pages only take into account the semesters for which complete information was available. Looking also at the data in Appendix 2, we see that, for Naples, the revenues ranged between 40,250 and 12 pieces of eight per semester ([Figure 4](#)). High fluctuations were determined by shocking exogenous events, such as the plague epidemics that affected Naples and Genoa in 1656, or by exceptional donations.

Figure 4. Income, expenses and balances per semester, *commissariato* of Naples, 1651–1659.

Source: Elaboration of the author based on data in Appendix 2.

The median income was 676 pieces of eight, that of the expenditures was 92, and that of the balances was 261 pieces of eight. Similar figures are attested for the Sicilian *commissariato*, another Spanish viceroyalty. Revenues in Sicily ranged from around 6200 to 800 pieces of eight, with a median of 3426 (Figure 5). The medians of expenditures and balances respectively were 2917 and 988 pieces of eight.

Incomes between Sicily and Naples – reducing the Neapolitan ones to an average of seven semesters to get the same amount of Sicilian semesters – are comparable, the latter's being only 14 per cent higher.

In Naples, large donation came directly from public assets. They were almost immediately followed by the sending of money to Jerusalem, so that balances always remained positive but minimal. The peak in the first half of 1652, for example, was due to the donation by the Viceroy the Count of Oñate of 40,000 pieces of eight.³¹ The money

Figure 5. Income, expenses and balances per semester, *commissariato* of Sicily, 1657–1660.

Source: Elaboration of the author based on data in Appendix 2.

arrived through the payment of 36,000 ducats from the *Banco della Pietà* of Naples, as arranged by the general of the Franciscan Order in Messina, friar John of Naples.

Quotas from the sale of many of the Neapolitan viceroyalty's taxes (*arrendamenti sulle tratte*) were also allocated annually to the Holy Land, which thus depended directly on the performance of the local economy.³² Since the fourteenth century, the Neapolitan kings swore to maintain the Franciscans in the Holy Land in perpetuity and at their own expense, a task that was inherited by the Spanish crown (D'Andrea 1983). Accounting records mention the proceeds of the revenues, often paid by the main banks in Naples.³³ In addition to tax revenues, there were also fixed incomes: the annual donation from the viceroy of 10 *cantara* of wool (about 0.9 ton) 'to clothe the religious men in the Holy Land'; 28 *carri* of wheat (about 41 tons); the rents of the houses situated in Naples at the '*Dochesca*', in the eastern part of town, and those in the western part of the Spanish quarters, the '*mortelle*'.³⁴ Wheat and wool were regularly re-sold.

Funds from Spain and other *commissariati* also converged on Naples. In May 1656, despite the plague, gold and silver coins arrived from Portugal – perhaps originally from Brazil – via Rome.³⁵ In 1658, a bill of exchange of 5940 Spanish pieces of eight was sent by the *commissario* of the Holy Land in Spain, Friar Antonio of Castille.³⁶ Wills drafted in the Spanish territories pertaining to the Holy Land were collected in Naples, before being sent to Jerusalem, such as a payment of about 100 pieces of eight sent by the Marquise de Poza in Madrid, which was collected through the *Banco di San Giacomo*.³⁷

The typologies of accounting entries were similar in the *commissariato* of Messina. Donations and sales of goods, in this case silk, along with transfers of funds from Spain on behalf of private individuals and of the *commissario* in Madrid, were common. In addition, the bishops of Catania and Syracuse – who were recorded as debtors in the document – sent regular payments.³⁸

The *commissariato* in Messina specialised in two specific operations within the Custody's network: the purchase of Venetian *zecchini*, along with Spanish or Sardinian pieces of eight, and their shipping to Jerusalem with other objects and pilgrims. Silver currencies were bought all year round and shipped as soon as the opportunity arose. These purchases made a specific category in the records, although they were sometimes integrated into the balance drawn up in Sicilian *onze*, when more expenses had to be met by the *commissario* and thus there was a risk of being illiquid. Silver currency was essential to face ordinary and extraordinary expenses in the Ottoman Empire's provinces (Pamuk 2004). Ships leaving Messina usually called at Malta, where there was another *commissariato*.

The Franciscans also seem to have been involved in smuggling operations. On 20 August 1657, in Messina, they recorded the payment of 12 *tari* (a little less than one piece of eight) for 'a gift that was given to the guard not to see the stuff that I was taking to Malta'.³⁹ The friars maybe wanted to avoid taxation or delays by custom houses. In the example cited, the voyage involved foodstuffs such as cheese and salmon, liturgical items such as a silver chalice for a Maronite priest, medicines for the Custody's infirmary, two pavilions to be given to the Ottoman pasha of Gaza and his secretary, woven silk cloths, and silver currency. Reconstructing the total value of the goods shipped on this route based on the accounting records is a complex operation due to the large number of items and account entries involved, not explicitly linked to the voyage.

Figure 6. Income, expenses and balances per semester, *commissariato* of Genoa, 1654–1687.

Source: Elaboration of the author based on data in Appendix 2.

Finally, the Genoese accounts follow. The *commissariato* was a key junction for the passage of pilgrims and alms between the Western Mediterranean and the Italian Peninsula (Tramontana 2023b, 222). However, the republic invested less in the prestige associated with the Holy Land, so the figures are lower than in the previous cases (Figure 6). They range between 1120 and 9 pieces of eight, with a median of 170 pieces of eight. The medians of expenditures and balances were 131 and 51 pieces of eight, despite the irregular cash flows seen in Figure 3. As can be seen in Appendix 1, the maximum income recorded in Genoa accounted to 4397 pieces of eight, a small sum compared to the money flowing through Naples and Messina. The 1677 accounts even contain a justification for the fact that no alms were collected between 1657 and 1659 due to the plague epidemics.⁴⁰

The Genoese *commissariato* was the one which relied most on alms and bequeaths by private individuals, collected through local institutions. These accounts also reflect the monetary uncertainties of the economy of the *Ancien Régime*, as there are frequent references to counterfeit or low-value coins that the friars sold to goldsmiths at a lower price.⁴¹

In addition to the Franciscan procurators, other local public authorities, such as notaries and chiefs of small settlements, regularly collected alms in the region.⁴² The Senate stepped in to recommend itinerant preachers to gather money for the Holy Land.⁴³ All alms converged in Genoa towards the Magistrate of the Poor (*Magistrato dei Poveri*).⁴⁴ This proto-welfare institution was used to redeem the religiously inappropriate behaviour of the ruling class of the republic, also criticised by PF, by redistributing alms among the poor and religious institutions (Marti 2021, 204).⁴⁵

The money from the Magistrate reached the local *commissariato* through the *Banco di San Giorgio*. The *Casa di San Giorgio*, to which the *Banco* was attached, was a semi-private body made up of Genoese patricians to which the republic turned when it needed liquidity, entrusting in return the collection of specific taxes and duties.⁴⁶ The charity that the Genoese provided through the Magistrate of the Poor usually consisted of both cash and the donation of portions of the public debt invested in *San Giorgio* that guaranteed more or less regular interest. It is not clear whether some of the funds managed by *San Giorgio* and mentioned in the *commissariato's* accounts came from such interests on shares of the

public debt.⁴⁷ This was the case in Spain, where the Pious Charity for the Holy Places (*Obra Pia de los Santos Lugares*) of Jerusalem had its founding capital invested in long-term, low-interest forms of public debt (*juros*).⁴⁸

Similar to the foreign currencies in Messina, *San Giorgio's* bills were recorded as a specific category in the accounts. In 1684, when the fleet of Louis XIV bombarded Genoa to dissuade the republic from strengthening its navy, the *commissario* registered 15 bills worth about 1785 pieces of eight that were transferred to the deputy-commissary in La Spezia for safety reasons, resulting in a significant expenditure.⁴⁹ Up until 1687, the bills were not sent back to Genoa, despite still being in the region.

Results

The way accounting was presented by the *commissariati* to PF reflected one main concern: showing liquidity. This concern probably determined the extreme variability in the time periods when balances were calculated to choose the most convenient intervals, when only positive ones could be displayed. Figure 3 and Appendix 1 reflect this phenomenon clearly.

The *sindaci's* coffers were always presented as solvent, without falling into opulence. Presenting a minimal positive balance was a way to show to PF the self-sufficiency of the *commissariato*, the honesty of the *sindaco*, the respect of the vow of poverty, and the smooth running of the accounts in a fair balance between charges and discharges being sent to Jerusalem or Rome.⁵⁰ This strategy complies with the two views on solvency illustrated by Pentikäinen (1984), mentioned in the Introduction. By showing positive balances, the *commissariati* proved to PF their capacity to meet their obligations in the short term, while guaranteeing their own continued existence through the direct handling of irregular cash flows in the long term.

Through all the examined *commissariati's* records – especially Naples and Messina – significant quantities of money flowed in and out. The friars placed themselves in a permanent state of need, which allowed and accelerated the circulation of resources. However, perhaps partly for religious, political and prestige reasons, the *commissariati* did not want to show their lack of liquidity or, even worse, of solvency. When they faced more expenditures than usual – usually because of travelling friars to take care of – they did not recur to indebtedness, but rather to a reduction in expenditure pending the arrival of new resources in the form of donations or money transfers from other *commissariati*.⁵¹ All balances were minimally positive as they were used to build a specific narrative (Matringe and Power 2024). These instances are further examples of the ambiguity of the charge-and-discharge system and of its poor performance for information gathering for management purposes, as envisaged by PF.

The variety of revenues sheds further light on the very diverse investments of the Custody, and the difficulty of PF to effectively monitor such operations, which were only vaguely categorised. Money from real estate seems to be almost completely absent, and regular income is almost negligible compared to occasional donations. Alms from the faithful that were mentioned in the records were barely enough – or sometimes largely insufficient – to cover ordinary expenses, such as maintenance of the *commissariati's* rooms inside the convents, the purchase of clothes and shoes for the friars, and their mobility on sea and land routes. Reliance on public institutions was crucial.

Conclusion

As a general rule, mendicant orders in Europe survived thanks to different types of revenues (Bertrand 2004). Alms and preaching fees, which were sometimes hardly distinguishable, were a way to obtain semi-regular revenues. In addition, there were other revenues such as donations, bequests and transfer of funds from other religious institutions. From the earliest times, often these revenues were not enough and the Franciscan monasteries resorted to indebtedness (Lenoble 2013, 255). Even the Custody's documents from the seventeenth century report the continuous payment of interest on loans (Heyberger 2021, 319), while the friars frequently wrote books and sermons addressed to the European rulers and nobility, perceived as generous sponsors (Heyberger 2021, 313).

Catholic rulers, in competition with each other, wanted to perpetuate the crusading ethos and promote their role as protectors over the Holy Land (Heyberger 2021, 314). The Custody's *commissariati*, therefore, in addition to having their procurators travelling far and wide collecting money and goods, received valuable assets by local rulers and institutions. The Franciscan Order asked them not to get into debts, as their purpose was to cover debts and expenses of the Custody itself. Most of *commissariati's* assets were sent to the Holy Land in a second stage, but first they helped them to take care of their expenses and to show their impeccable functioning.

Framing the Custody and its branches from a corporative perspective, with a defined hierarchal structure and an external supervisor authority, highlights the importance of themes usually not associated with religious organisations, such as liquidity and economic solvency. The focus on an early modern trans-imperial religious institution that acted as a sort of proto-multinational corporation with interests in Europe and the Middle East helps in shedding light on these topics. Early modern clear-cut examples of accounting for management purposes are hard to find, even with a broad definition of the term. The analysis of the *commissariati's* records did not reveal solely their accounting structure, but also their relationship with the supervising authority, PF, and the difficulties of the early modern Papacy to effectively monitor its entities (Emich 2023).

Although accounting supervision does not necessarily offer the picture of everyday reality that took place in a *commissariato*, the interest of religious accounts in general, as also emphasised by Lenoble (2013, 111), lies in the way in which they concretely participate, as a technique, in the daily organisation of conventual life and in the production of a narrative. The narrative built by the *commissariati* for PF showed their corporate solvency in the short and long term. This concern resulted from both the irregular timing for the calculation and sending of balances, and from the choice of the most convenient intervals. In this way, almost all *commissariati's* account extracts presented regular and minimally positive values. Irregular cash flows from Europe allowed the friars in Jerusalem to efficiently administer their assets while also resorting to the local loan market.

The message the *commissari* wanted to convey to PF was that of a financially healthy organisation, capable of keeping its accounts in order while regularly achieving full economic solvency. Thus, the *commissari* could continue enjoying a wide decision-making leeway necessary to manage irregular cash flows. According to Gryglewicz (2011), if a firm is persistent in liquidity surprises, either positive or negative, they stop being surprising. I believe this was the view according to which the *commissariati* operated in practice, although they did not want to show this precariousness to their supervisors and therefore,

slightly altered their records, with the *sindaci* covering temporary debts. The obligation to achieve solvency is not necessarily part of the concept of accountability; nor is transparency (Fox 2007), a confusion that usually involves erroneous distinctions (Llibrer Escrig and Villaluenga de Gracia 2023, 2). Starting from very different backgrounds and tools compared to the Jesuits studied by Quattrone (2004), the Franciscans reached the same objective: separation from wealth, good keeping of the accounts, and humble poverty.

Franciscan poverty was founded on its inherent flexibility, carefully shaped by the dynamic interplay between man's spiritual connection to God and the constantly evolving socio-economic environment (McClure 2019, 337). Their bookkeeping was firstly designed as an instrument for building and monitoring moderate and controlled poverty (Lenoble 2013, 368). Franciscan history reminds us that one of the earliest forms of globalisation, the attempt to extend the local conception of a mendicant community on a global scale by adopting a corporative structure, was driven not by the desire for wealth accumulation but by the pursuit of poverty and evangelisation.

Notes

1. Acting in good faith while promoting the growth of the enterprise – the Custody of the Holy Land, in this case – was a frequent admonition in the Holy Land legislation, ordering the *commissari* not to incur debts and to carry out all operations necessary for good governance, debt relief and the preservation of the holy places and the Franciscans (Vaginari vol. III/1, 445).
2. See, for instance, Bertrand 2004; Quattrone 2004; Bériou and Chiffolleau 2009; Lenoble 2013; Gomes, Maran, and Araújo 2022. For a complete overview, see Corderly 2015 and the bibliography therein quoted.
3. We should not forget that the basic concepts of management control are shared by both for-profit and nonprofit organisations (Duncan, Flesher, and Stocks 1999).
4. Other branches being the Conventual (formed in 1517) and the Capuchins (formed in 1520). On the Observants' rule of the Custody and the narrative they created, see Evangelisti 2024.
5. On missionary activities and accounting practices, see Tramontana, Vu Thanh, and Windler forthcoming. On the progressive involvement of the Franciscan in market dynamics, see Todeschini (1994; 2004) and Evangelisti (2015).
6. Archivio Storico Propaganda Fide (ASPF), Scritture riferite nei Congressi (SC), Terra Santa (TS) misc. 3, cc. 18v–22v. The payments sent from the *commissariati* to Jerusalem were called *condotte*, which were recorded there in specific books, partially published by Quecedo (1951). Since 1616, there is a reference to the 'big debts' (*gran debito*) of the Custody (13). Following the *condotta* of 15 October 1630 (28–29) all pending debts were repaid. The following payments were probably used to increase the Custody's presence and assets in the Holy Land, as well as to repay occasional new debts (43).
7. On this topic, see Carnevali forthcoming, to whom I am grateful for her useful references on the relationship between PF and the *commissariati*.
8. On the Custody see Golubovich 1906-1939; Piccirillo 1983; del Buey and Alvi 2005; Ritsema van Eck 2019; Bartolomei Romagnoli et al. 2020; Evangelisti 2020a.
9. Even Melchiorre (2016, 53) used the concept of organisational charts to study the economic activities of religious institutions.
10. Respectively: the Roman Law; the eleventh–thirteenth centuries revivers of Roman legal scholarship in European universities; the medieval Germanic tribal traditions; the English guilds; the *maona* or the *Casa di San Giorgio* (1407–1805) of Genoa (Taviani 2022, 1 and bibliography therein); the Church and Canon Law (Harris 2020, 255–258). Even in modern times, theoretically, Catholic entrepreneurs and companies were guided by an upward accountability to God (Lazzini, Lazzini, and Balluchi 2023).

11. Corporate notions played some role in the conceptualisation of rulers and states as well (Maitland 1900; 1901; Kantorowicz 1970).
12. Despite Venice's declining importance in the Eastern Mediterranean compared to the previous century, it was still a major player in the network of the Custody (Setti forthcoming). Unfortunately, there are only sporadic extracts from the account books of the Venetian *commissariato*, so it is currently impossible to use these sources. In competition to the Italian and Spanish networks, France used its Ottoman status as Protector of the Holy Places to establish its own network, trying without success to transform the Custody into a French Catholic institution (Armstrong 2021, 8).
13. ASPF, SC, TS misc. 3, 1645, cc. 31r-42v.
14. On 17 September 1659, friar Alessio Carabaxal, general *commissario* of the Holy Land in Sicily, left the convent of Santa Maria di Gesù, in Messina, to personally deliver the accounts of his *commissariato* to the general *commissario* of Spain in Madrid. At the same time, he paid a translator to write a copy in vernacular Italian that was sent to PF in Rome for the same reason. ASPF, SC, TS misc. 1, *Conti [...] di Sicilia* 09/12/1660, 20/11/1660.
15. It was a prestigious appointment, conferred to wealthy families. This is probably one of the reasons why, compared to the reeves in charge of accounting in parishes (Noke 1991), no case of frauds has been found so far among the *commissariati's sindaci*.
16. ASPF, SC, TS misc. 3, 1645, cc. 31r-42v.
17. ASPF, Acta 23, 16/11/1654, f. 114r-118r.
18. Unfortunately, the copies of the records that the *commissariati* sent to Spain are still missing. We do not know whether they followed the same strategies.
19. ASPF, SC, TS vol. 10, c. 200, no date.
20. ASPF, SC, TS misc. 1, *Conti [...] di Genova* 29/09/1683, f. 2.
21. '*summa, qualitas, et quantitas eleemosynarum [...] ut solidationem et sententiam super propria officii administratione quilibet referre et reportare possit et valeat in forma valida*'. ASPF, Acta 23, 16/11/1654, 117r.
22. Among those analysed so far, only the records of the Rome *commissariato* bear the expressions charge and discharge. See ASPF, SC, TS misc. 1, *Conti [...] di Roma*, 1657–1658. On the description and comparison between several charge-and-discharge accounts, see Jones (1985).
23. For example, in 1679, the *commissariato* of Hungary, on which we have only indirect sources, sent a bill of exchange to Livorno via Venice to help the local *commissariato* paying a ransom for a friar imprisoned in Tunis. This represented an unexpected peak in the *commissariato's* expenditures for that year. See ASPF, SC, TS misc. 1, *Conti [...] di Toscana*, 31/01/1679.
24. ASPF, SC, TS misc. 3, *Conti [...] di Genova* 04/12/1668, 04/12/1668; ASPF, SC, TS misc. 1, *Conti [...] di Sicilia* 09/12/1660, 24/01/1658.
25. ASPF, Acta 23, 16/11/1654, f. 117r.
26. ASPF, SC, TS misc. 1, 18/06/1666, f. 122.
27. A similar attitude has been observed in the charge-and-discharge accounts used by administrators of religious funds in Manila (Rivas Moreno 2021).
28. Archives Nationales de France, Mar/B/7/73, 22/09/1706. The French *commissariato* wrote three copies of their accounting records: one for their convent, one for the Franciscan General Chapter, and one for the King of France. On the relationship between the kingdom and the Custody see Collin (1983).
29. On the project's database and activities see Carnevali and Lastilla (2024); <https://holylab-erc.uniroma3.it/>.
30. ASPF, Acta 31, 28/02/1662, f. 19v.
31. ASPF, Scritture Originali Riferite nelle Congregazioni Generali (SOCG) 197, *Conti [...] di Napoli* 31/12/1656, 02/04/1652. Another significant donation from Naples, of 10,000 ducats, was made in 1612 (Barriuso 1992, 208).
32. On the *arrendamenti*, see De Rosa (1958), Bulgarelli (1993, 23) and bibliography quoted therein.

33. Such as the royal customs of Naples, through the *Banco dello Spirito Santo*; the salt of Apulia, through the *Banco del Popolo*; the tax on eggs and goats, through the *Banco di San Giorgio*; the tax on fish, through the *Banco di San Giacomo*; the *saccheria* of Bari, through bills of exchange paid in Naples; the tax of the *mezzo peso*, varying according to the weight of manufactured goods; the tax on new flour; the tax of one ducat per barrel; the tax on *fondachi* and customs of Apulia. ASPF, SC, TS misc. 1, *Conti [...] di Napoli*, no date [1660?]; ASPF, SC, TS misc. 1, *Conti [...] di Napoli* 03/08/1658.
34. ASPF, SOCG 197, *Conti [...] di Napoli* 31/12/1656. Sources also mention a 'house book', probably compiled only to keep track of rents, which is currently lost.
35. ASPF, SOCG 197, *Conti [...] di Napoli* 31/12/1656, 31/05/1656.
36. ASPF, SC, TS misc. 1, *Conti [...] di Napoli*, no date [1660?], 12/09/1658.
37. ASPF, SC, TS misc. 1, *Conti [...] di Napoli*, no date [1660?], 19/06/1660.
38. As for the bishop of Catania, it seems that the payments had been ordered by the viceroy and confirmed by the pope himself for 20 years. See ASPF, SC, TS misc. 1, *Conti [...] di Sicilia* 09/12/1660, 09/09/1658.
39. ASPF, SC, TS misc. 1, *Conti [...] di Sicilia* 09/12/1660, 20/08/1657.
40. ASPF, SC, TS misc. 1, *Conti [...] di Genova* 30/12/1678.
41. They were recorded at their intrinsic value, but the entries also show their nominal values. See, for instance, ASPF, SC, TS misc. 1, *Conti [...] di Genova* 16/04/1688, 17/07/1686.
42. ASPF, SC, TS misc. 1, *Conti [...] di Genova* 10/09/1698, 19/10/1697; ASPF, SC, TS misc. 3, *Conti [...] di Genova* 16/01/1682, 25/04/1680.
43. ASPF, SC, TS misc. 1, *Conti [...] di Genova* 04/12/1668, 27/03/1667.
44. ASPF, SC, TS misc. 3, *Conti [...] di Genova* 16/01/1682, 16/02/1682. It is believed that the Magistrate developed during the XIV century from a temporary office that distributed alms on the occasion of religious holidays (Petti Balbi 2013).
45. On the religious attitude of Genoese merchants as seen from PF see *Miscellanee varie XIII/a, Compendiosa e generosa relatione [...]*, 1677.
46. The *Banco* was founded in 1408 with the function of deposit and credit, later evolving in a more complex institution (Cama 2006, 109–120; Taviani 2022, 47–52).
47. This document, found in the Genoese archives, would confirm such hypothesis. State Archive of Genoa, *San Giorgio, Affari Generali* 3154, 1640. However, further research will be needed.
48. This institution, founded by the Spanish Monarchy to finance the Custody, functioned according to virtuous credit circulation mechanisms typical of institutions based on the Franciscan economy (Filioli Uranio 2023). Spain also funded the Catholic Church through the *Colectoría*, a committee charged with the task of collecting the revenues of the vacant bishoprics and channeling them to Rome (Carretero Zamora 2013).
49. ASPF, SC, TS misc. 1, *Conti [...] di Genova* 16/04/1688, 22/06/1686.
50. As aforementioned, PF aimed to monitor the *commissariati's* economic activities. This concern can be seen in the introductory notes that the *commissari* sent with their account extracts. For example, the Genoese *commissario* friar Giovanni Ghersi wrote a note in 1686 to boast about the amount of alms collected and the absence of debts in his commission (ASPF, SC, TS misc. 1, *Conti [...] di Genova* 19/01/1686). Ghersi himself, in 1688, explicitly mentioned an anonymous memoir sent to PF in previous years, which criticised his economic management. According to his hypothesis, the memoir was written by 'those who are indebted to our Holy Order' (ASPF, SC, TS misc. 1, *Conti [...] di Genova* 16/04/1688).
51. The comparisons with other account extracts, currently under scrutiny, revealed that indebtedness was a very rare occurrence. Sporadic evidence of payments for the *commissariati's* debts can be found, for instance, in the accounts of the *commissariato* of Rome for the seventeenth century (ASPF, SC, TS misc. 1, *Conti [...] di Roma* 31/12/1662, 04/01/1661), or in those of Genoa for the eighteenth century (ASPF, SC, TS misc. 1, *Conti [...] di Genova* 16/08/1735, 04/05/1734).

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Data availability statement

The data from the accounting records of the *commissariati* have been digitised as part of the ERC project HolyLab – A global economic organisation in the early modern period: The Custody of the Holy Land through its account books (1600–1800) (Grant ID: 101001857). They will soon be available online in an open access database. Please contact the author for updates.

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Appendices

Appendix 1. Tables with income, expenses and balances from the *commissariati* of Naples, Genoa, and Messina as resulting from the records and converted into Spanish pieces of eight.

Genoa, 1654-1687							
Time Period	Income	Exp.	Balance	Time Period	Income	Exp.	Balance
1654/12-1656	287.0	187.7	99.2	02-1672/06-1672	1039.3	1006.3	32.9
07-1664			24.6	06-1672/11-1672	53.1	35.3	17.8
09-1664/12-1664	50.7	17.5	33.2	12-1672/06-1674	497.0	427.5	82.7
01-1665/06-1665	164.9		164.9	06-1674/12-1674	290.6	247.3	43.2
07-1665/06-1666	348.4	149.8	198.5	12-1674/03-1676	1510.0	1506.7	3.2
06-1666/01-1667	241.6	200.6	41.0	04-1676/11-1676	96.1	54.7	41.4
05-1666/05-1668	222.2	213.9	8.2	11-1676/11-1677	560.7	553.4	7.3
12-1668			53.1	12-1677/12-1678	103.6	55.5	48.1
03-1667/07-1667	502.0			12-1678/04-1679	1097.6	1014.4	83.2
08-1667/12-1668	1859.0	501.9		05-1679/12-1679	139.3	39.4	99.9
05-1668/12-1668	252.5	126.0	126.5	02-1680/04-1681	567.6	351.0	18.0
11-1668/04-1669	169.1	170.7	-1.5	04-1681/12-1681	1190.2	253.5	78.5
05-1669/11-1669	1332.6	127.8	51.1	03-1682/11-1682	1965.9	23.3	1942.6
11-1669/11-1670	139.0	136.1	2.9	01-1684/11-1685	4397.2	2308.9	123.6
12-1670/12-1671	231.0	146.9	84.0	03-1686/12-1687	2993.7	1052.5	197.8

Sicily, 1657-1660			
Time Period	Income ¹	Exp.	Balance
04-1657/05-1657	3820.1	175.6	3641.6
05-1657/09-1657	3911.1	2550.0	1361.1
10-1657/11-1657	1638.8	72.2	1563.8
12-1657/01-1658	2488.8	480.5	1272.2
01-1658/04-1658	3161.1	166.6	2258.3
05-1658/08-1658	4947.2	4150.0	797.2
08-1658/10-1658	2286.1	341.6	1544.4
10-1658/12-1658	2033.3	197.2	1836.1
12-1658/04-1659	8096.3	586.1	7294.4
04-1659/07-1659	8061.1	3347.2	4688.8
07-1659/08-1659	10045.8	4088.8	825.0
08-1659/09-1659			494.4
09-1659/01-1660	9112.7	1188.8	630.5
01-1660/03-1660	850.0	313.8	536.1
03-1660/05-1660	600.0	44.4	555.5
05-1660/06-1660			538.8
06-1660/12-1660	9376.9	166.6	716.6

¹Figures in the income column reflect the total values of Sicilian *onze*, Venetian *zecchini* and Spanish pieces of eight, recorded separately in the sources. Discrepancies in the numbers result from the decimals being rounded off.

Naples, 1651-1661			
Time Period	Income	Exp.	Balance
06-1651			261.8
07-1651/05-1652	45314.5	44855.8	458.7
06-1652/05-1654	1710.7	1343.1	367.6
09-1654/03-1656	3852.4	3743.3	109.1
03-1656/06-1656	906.4	63.5	843.7
07-1651/12-1656	51068.6	50248.0	820.6
01-1657			533.5
01-1657/05-1658	2562.1	1672.0	889.9
08-1658/02-1659	983.4	696.3	287.1
10-1658/02-1659	7503.1	7260.0	243.1
08-1658/01-1661	3075.6	2312.2	762.3
09-1658/01-1661	14502.4	13965.6	536.8

Appendix 2. Tables with income, expenses and balances from the *commissariati* of Naples, Genoa, and Messina manually calculated based on the data from the records and converted into Spanish pieces of eight.

Genoa, 1654-1687							
Time Period	Income	Exp.	Balance	Time Period	Income	Exp.	Balance
07-12/1654	14.9	10.3	4.6	07-12/1674	198.2	213.9	-15.7
01-06/1655	9.2	43.1	-33.8	01-06/1675	428.9		428.9
07-12/1655	13.2	12.8	0.4	07-12/1675	53.0		53.0
01-06/1656	174.9	121.0	53.8	01-06/1676	1004.8	1001.9	2.9
07-12/1656	49.2			07-12/1676	901.1	313.3	587.7
01-06/1657	24.2			01-06/1677	56.8	143.7	-86.9
01-06/1664			24.6	07-12/1677	463.3	400.1	63.1
07-12/1664	26.2	17.3	8.8	01-06/1678	6.5	31.9	-25.4
01-06/1665	130.9		130.9	07-12/1678	90.7	22.6	68.0
07-12/1665	33.9	148.0	-114.1	01-06/1679	1119.3	1014.3	104.9
01-06/1666	155.1	0.4	154.7	07-12/1679	34.7	38.4	-3.7
07-12/1666	48.6	188.0	-139.3	01-06/1680	89.6	314.0	-224.4
01-06/1667	496.1	582.4	-86.2	07-12/1680	475.4	34.4	441.0
07-12/1667	104.0	173.9	-69.8	01-06/1681	479.8	257.0	222.8
01-06/1668	234.5	239.7	-5.2	07-12/1681	340.8	1.2	339.6
07-12/1668	977.9	26.8	951.1	01-06/1682	681.0	22.0	659.0
01-06/1669	60.8	167.4	-106.6	07-12/1682	742.0		742.0
07-12/1669	192.3	123.4	68.8	01-06/1683	253.2	0.2	253.0
01-06/1670	75.5	7.5	67.9	07-12/1683	166.6	20.6	146.0
07-12/1670		201.3	-201.3	01-06/1684	25.0	1786.4	-1761.4
01-06/1671	175.9	48.1	127.7	07-12/1684	58.2	226.2	-168.0
07-12/1671	53.9	22.9	31.0	01-06/1685	196.0	131.0	65.0
01-06/1672	995.7	1010.4	-14.7	07-12/1685	206.4	125.2	81.2
07-12/1672	18.4	35.1	-16.6	01-06/1686	334.8	184.0	150.8
01-06/1673	445.8	396.6	49.1	07-12/1686	20.2	247.2	-227.0
07-12/1673	30.0	40.5	-10.4	01-06/1687	461.4	383.2	78.2
01-06/1674	502.1	9.7	492.4	07-12/1687	312.4	202.4	110.0

Naples, 1651–1660			
Time Period	Income	Exp.	Balance
01-06/1651		104.5	261.8
07-12/1651	5090.8	4975.3	115.5
01-06/1652	40250.1	39771.6	478.5
07-12/1652	12.1		
01-06/1653		68.2	
07-12/1653	982.3	59.4	922.9
01-06/1654	63.8	1369.5	-1305.7
07-12/1654	35.2	36.3	-1.1
01-06/1655	83.6	203.5	-119.9
07-12/1655	55.0	35.2	19.8
01-06/1656	4183.3	3454.0	729.3
07-12/1656	33.0	55.0	-22.0
01-06/1657	1478.4	1141.8	336.6
07-12/1657	567.6	50.6	517.0
01-06/1658	785.4	80.3	705.1
07-12/1658	7398.6	7979.4	-580.8
01-06/1659	42.9	1098.9	-1056.0
07-12/1659	2951.3		
01-06/1660	2986.5		
07-12/1660	2030.6		

Sicily, 1657-1660			
Time Period	Income ²	Exp.	Balance
07-12/1657	951.8	3010.9	-2059.1
01-06/1658	3700.7	2371.1	1329.6
07-12/1658	2706.2	2917.4	-211.2
01-06/1659	6185.1	3797.6	2387.4
07-12/1659	5755.6	4767.1	988.4
01-06/1660	792.4	1394.5	-602.0
07-12/1660	3426.5	108.0	3318.5

²Figures in the income column reflect the total values of Sicilian *onze*, Venetian *zecchini* and Spanish pieces of eight, recorded separately in the sources. Discrepancies in the numbers result from the decimals being rounded off.